

Analysis of the Role of SMEs in Indonesia's Economic Growth in 2009-2018

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ABSTRACT

SMEs are considered to have an important role in encouraging the accelerated increase in per capita income and the improvement of the economy of a region. SMEs players are required to develop the economy of a country and compete between countries, so that they are able to advance the Indonesian economy. The data used in this research are secondary data from the Central Bureau of Statistics, the Ministry of Cooperatives and SMEs and literature studies related to this research. The dependent variable in this study is Indonesia's Gross Domestic Product (GDP), the independent variable used is the variable total of SMEs, the total of labor SME, investment and exports. This research uses multiple linear regression method. The purpose of this study was to analyze the effect of the total of SMEs, the effect of the total of labor SME, the effect of investment and the influence of exports from the SME sector on Indonesia's GDP. From the research results, it is known that the variables of the total of SMEs, investment and exports have no effect on GDP. It is different from the total of SME labor variable which significantly affects GDP. Overall the SME sector can affect Indonesia's economic growth.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the era of globalization, economic growth is very important in a country to increase regional economic income so that it can improve the welfare of its people (Jauhar and Roziq 2019).

In Indonesia, SMEs are seen as having an important role in increasing per capita income and the economy of a region. SMEs are required to be more responsive to consumer demands that are increasingly specific, unique and at affordable prices but with quality products (Kustono and Agustini 2019). Until now, SMEs are one of the main contributions to economic growth because they can create jobs, increase exports and GDP (Octavia, Effendi, and Prasetyo 2019).

The main drivers of the Indonesian economy are SMEs that can absorb a lot of labor, play an important role in increasing per capita

income, so that they can create a better market and always try to innovate in business activities and become actors in evaluating the international balance of payments through export activities and saving foreign exchange through imported products related to SMEs (Amilia, Puspita, and Putra 2021).

SME problems related to capital are resolved with demand and funding assistance, so research is needed to address these problems which will have an even better impact on further economic growth (Juliprijanto, Sarfiah, and others 2017).

Economic growth in Indonesia by SMEs can be measured by the GDP growth of SMEs (Kustono, Mas'ud, and Magvira 2019). SME GDP growth is influenced by several sectors such as: Total of labor SMEs, SME exports, number of

SME units, SME investment (Hakim, Tobing, and Istifadah 2019).

Table 1.1 is a table of data on Indonesian MSMEs in 2013-2016 which shows that an increase in the total of SMEs, an increase in the total of labor SMEs, an increase in investment and an increase in exports have a positive impact on GDP.

Table 1. GDP, Number of MSMEs, Number of MSME Workforce, Investment, Exports (2013-2016)

Tahun	2013	2014	2015	2016
PDB (Milyar Rupiah)	5,440,007.90	10,569,705.30	11,531,716.90	12,406,809.80
Jumlah UKM (Unit)	57.895.721	58.444.657	59.262.772	59.890.487
Jumlah Tenaga Kerja UKM (Orang)	114.144.082	119.050.288	132.379.684	134.632.315
Investasi (Milyar Rupiah)	1.655.233,5	1.688.338,2	1.722.105	1.761.816,7
Ekspor (US\$ Milyar)	182.112,70	185.833,49	192.573,60	199.313,57

Source: BPS, 2017

Nasution (2018) conducted research on the Role of SMEs on Economic Growth in Indonesia. The results of this study explain that the SME and export units have a positive and significant effect on economic growth in Indonesia (Tobing 2020). This is aimed at the results of the partial t multiple linear regression test which shows a sig. of 0.000 in the SMEs and Export unit variable. The simultaneous F multiple linear regression test shows that the sig is 0.005. The two results of the multiple linear regression test are smaller than the 0.05 test (Nasution 2018).

Resalawati (2011) conducted a study on "The Influence of SME Development on Economic Growth in the SME Sector in Indonesia". Research shows that the number of SME units and SME investment has a significant positive effect on economic growth in Indonesia (Sumani and Roziq 2020). In contrast to the number of SME and investment units, the workforce variable in the SME sector has no effect on economic growth, possibly because the workforce is not absorbed optimally (Sulianti Kristina TOBING et al. 2021). In this study, several theories explain that the export variable is the most dominant variable and the fastest to influence economic development (Ade Raselawati and Ilmu Ekonomi Dan Studi Pembangunan Fakultas Ekonomi Dan Bisnis 2011).

Hapsari et al. (2014) conducted a study on "The Influence of Small and Medium

Enterprise (SMEs) Growth on Regional Economic Growth (Study in Batu City Government) explained that the number of SMEs and workers had no effect on economic growth with a probability of SMEs of 0.1285 and a probability of employment. Amounting to 0.1495 (Hapsari et al. 2014).

In fact, Big Business (BB) in Indonesia is not able to absorb a workforce with a large population in Indonesia (Ely, Effendi, and Mas'ud 2020). SMEs exists as a business unit capable of absorbing labor, in accordance with the structure of labor-intensive SMEs (Purniawan, Mas'ud, and Wulandari 2019).

Support to increase the potential of SMEs in economic growth, namely from investors and the government by carrying out sustainable empowerment to support SME production (Arkundato et al. 2019). SMEs are able to compete in the global market if there are adequate facilities from the government (Ikmal Huda, Prihatini, and Paramu 2019). The Ministry of Cooperatives and SMEs has also promoted domestic and foreign products that are expected to be penetrated by the products of cooperatives, micro enterprises, small businesses and medium enterprises (H., Titisari, and . 2019).

The purpose of this researcher is to find out whether there is an influence of SMEs on Indonesia's Economic Growth to conduct research by looking at the variables of the SME workforce, the number of SME units, SME exports and investment in the SME sector on the effect of GDP on the SME sector from 2009 to 2018 (Prasetyo et al. 2020).

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND HYPOTHESES

SMEs

The criteria for SMEs is that small businesses have a workforce of 5-19 people, while for medium-sized enterprises have a workforce of 20 - 99 people. The criteria for SMEs can be seen in the following table:

Table 2. Criteria for MSMEs

CRITERIA	NET WORTH	SALES RESULTS ANNUAL
Micro Business	Max. 50 jt	Max. 300 jt
Small Business	> 50 jt – 500 jt	>300 jt – 2,5 M

Medium Enterprises	>500 jt – 10M	–	>2,5 M – 50 M
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Source: (Undang-Undang Republik Indonesia 2008)

Labor

The definition of labor, namely labor is usually found in the labor market which is ready to be used in the production or service process, then the company will ask for labor in the labor market (Sitanggang and Nachrowi 2004).

The factors that affect the demand for labor are the price of production, changes in technology, and the supply of other production factors (Sholeh 2009).

Investment

Investment is to postpone the consumption of goods or services in the present in order to get a greater consumption in the future, but there is a risk of uncertainty, therefore compensation is needed for the delay (Prasetyo 2020a). Investment in SMEs and Indonesian Growth (GDP) are closely linked (Prasetyo 2020b). If the use of public funding is greater than investment, it will have an effect on increasing the country's economic growth (Prasetyo 2020d).

Exports

Exports are the release of a product from the Indonesian customs area that will be sent abroad by complying with applicable regulations, especially customs regulations (Ginting 2017). Exports also have a negative impact if there are obstacles in these activities (Piluharto, Asnawati, and Roziq 2020). Export activities will run if they meet the requirements stipulated by law such as business licensing and carry out an optimal export activity strategy, it will increase economic growth (Prasetyo 2020c).

Economic growth

Factors that affect economic growth, namely:

- Economic factors, consisting of labor, division of labor and production scale, advances in technology and natural resources (SDA).
- Non-economic factors, consisting of culture, social, politics and administration.

The Solow growth model is used to determine how the influence of the growth of the workforce, growth in supply and technological progress on the output of services or goods in a country (Kurniawan and Hayati 2015).

Gross Domestic Product (GDP) is the value of all production of goods and services in a country which are produced by production factors owned by citizens of a country and foreign countries (Fadilah, Putro, and Mayes 2017).

Conceptual Framework

Hypotheses

- Ho: $\beta_1 \leq 0$. If probability $> \alpha$ then the variable number of SMEs has no effect on GDP. Ha: $\beta_1 > 0$. If probability $< \alpha$ then the variable number of SMEs has a significant effect on GDP.
- Ho: $\beta_1 \leq 0$. If probability $> \alpha$ then the variable number of SMEs workers has no effect on GDP. Ha: $\beta_1 > 0$. If probability $< \alpha$ then the variable number of SME workers has a significant effect on GDP.
- Ho: $\beta_1 \leq 0$. If probability $> \alpha$ then the investment variable has no effect on GDP. Ha: $\beta_1 > 0$. If probability $< \alpha$, then the investment variable has a significant effect on GDP.
- Ho: $\beta_1 \leq 0$. If probability $> \alpha$ then the export variable has no effect on GDP. Ha: $\beta_1 > 0$. If probability $< \alpha$ then the export variable has a significant effect on GDP.

3. RESEARCH METHOD

Design or Research Design

The method used in this research is quantitative research to test variables using data in the form of numbers and to analyze theories with statistical procedures.

Types and Sources of Data

Quantitative data types and data sources are secondary available at the Central Bureau of Statistics.

Population and Sample

The population is a group of people, events, or anything that has certain characteristics by the researcher (Hariyana et al. 2020). Population members are called population elements (W. Prasetyo 2021). Researchers can examine all elements of the population called a census or examine some of the population elements called samples (Amirullah 2015). This study uses a population-based data selection method consisting of the number of SMEs, labor SMEs, exports, investment and GDP in Indonesia (W. W. Prasetyo 2021).

Operational Definition of Variables.

Based on the formulation of the problem and the hypothesis being tested.

Dependent Variable

The dependent variable (dependent) is a variable that is influenced or caused by the independent variable (Sugiyono 2017). The dependent variable used in this study is Indonesia's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in 2009-2018, the unit of which is billion rupiah and is stated on the basis of current prices. The formula for calculating GDP is:

$$Y = C + G + I + (X - M)$$

Information:

C	= household expenses
G	= government expenditure
I	= investment
X - M	= export - import

Independent Variable

Independent variable (Free) is a variable that affects or causes the dependent variable (Sugiyono 2017). The following are some of the independent variables in this study:

- The number of units in the SME sector in 2009-2018 as measured in units.
- The number of workers in the SME sector in 2009-2018 as measured in people.
- Total investment value in the SME sector in 2009-2018 as measured in units of billions of rupiah.

- Total export value in the SME sector in 2009-2018 which is measured in units of billions of rupiah.

Data analysis method.

This study uses SPSS version 23 as a tool to test data.

Multiple Linear Regression Test

This study uses multiple linear regression analysis because the independent variables exceed two. This analysis method is used to measure how much influence the independent variable has on the dependent variable and predict it. This analysis model has the following equation:

$$Y = \alpha + b_1(X_1) + b_2(X_2) + b_3(X_3) + b_4(X_4) + e$$

Information:

Y	= economic growth or national GDP in 2009-2018.
α	= Constant coefficient
b	= Regression coefficient
X1	= Number of units in the SME sector in 2009-2018
X2	= Number of workers in the SME sector in 2009-2018
X3	= Total investment value in the SME sector in 2009-2018
X4	= Total export value in the SME sector in 2009-2018.
e	= error, disturbance variable.

This research uses multiple linear regression tests individually (t) and groups (F). Here's the explanation:

Individual Signification Test (Statistical t test).

The t statistical test is used to test the significance of the effect of each variable on the number of SMEs, the number of SME workers, investment and exports on Indonesia's GDP. The t statistical test formula is as follows:

$$t = (b_i - 0) / S = b_i / S$$

Information:

S = Standard Deviation, can be calculated with the root of the variance (S²) or SSE: Σ degrees of freedom. Formula:

$$S^2 = SSE / n - k$$

Information:

n = number of observations

k = number of parameters in the model including the intercept.

This study uses the t test using the sig t way. If the Sig t is less than 5% (0.05) then the independent variable will have an effect on the dependent variable, if the Sig t is greater than 5% (0.05) the independent variable will not affect the dependent variable.

Simultaneous Signification Test (F Statistical Test)

The F statistical test is used to simultaneously test the effect of each variable on the number of SMEs, the number of SME workers, investment and exports on Indonesia's GDP (Roos Ana, Budi Sulistiyo, and Prasetyo 2021). The F statistical test basically shows whether all the independent variables included in the model have a simultaneous influence on the dependent variable (Janie 2012). The formula for the F statistical test is as follows:

$$F = \frac{MSR}{MSE} = \left(\frac{SSR/k}{SSE/(n-k)} \right)$$

Information:

SSR = sum of squares due to regression = $\sum (\hat{Y} - y)^2$

SSE = sum of squares error = $\sum (Y_i - \hat{Y}_i)^2$

n = number of observations

k = number of parameters

MSR = mean of squares due to regression

MSE = mean of squares due to error.

This study uses the F test using sig F. If Sig F is less than 5% (0.05) then the independent variable will affect the dependent variable, if Sig F is greater than 5% (0.05) the independent variable has no effect on the dependent variable

Multiple linear regression analysis can be performed if the data has been tested for quality and classical tests. Here's the test model.

Data Quality Test

Validity test

Analysis of the validity in this study using confirmatory factor analysis (Confirmatory Factor Analysis) which aims to test whether the indicators used are valid or not (Afandi et al. 2022). A variable data is said to be valid if it provides a KMO and Bartlett's test value ≥ 0.5 and factor analysis (rules of thumb of loading factor score ≥ 0.4).

Reliability Test.

The reliability test function is used as a tool to measure indicators of the SMEs variable. Reliability can be measured using a numerical index called coefficient (Al-Fa'izah, Rahayu, and

Hikmah 2017). A construct or variable is said to be reliable if it gives a Cronbach Alpha value > 0.70 (Ghozali and Ratmono 2017).

Classic assumption test

Normality test

The normality test aims to test whether in the regression model, the SME variable data has a normal distribution (Azizah 2021). The normality test used in this study is the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. If the data from the Kolmogorov-Smirnov one-sample calculation results in a value above 0.05, the regression model can be said to be normal (Aji 2017). Conversely, if the data from the Kolmogorov-Smirnov one-sample calculation results in a value below 0.05, the regression model is not normal. (Ghozali and Ratmono 2017)

Heteroscedasticity Test

Heteroscedasticity test aims to test whether in the regression model there is an inequality of variance from the residuals of one observation to another (Setyanti, Sri Wahyu Lelly Hana, Yulisetiarini, Dyah, Para,u 2021). If the residual variance from one observation to another is constant, it is called Homoscedasticity and if it is different it is called Heteroscedasticity (Sumani, Roziq, and Annisa 2021). A good regression model is what occurs homoscedasticity or does not occur heteroscedasticity (Ghozali and Ratmono 2017).

Multicollinearity Test

The multicollinearity test aims to test whether the regression model has a correlation between independent (independent) variables. In this study, multicollinearity can be seen from the tolerance value and variance inflation factor (VIF). The cutoff value that is commonly used to indicate multicollinearity is the Tolerance value ≤ 0.10 or the same as the VIF value ≥ 10 (Ghozali and Ratmono 2017). The formula used is as follows:

$$VIF = \frac{1}{Tolerance} \text{ or } Tolerance = \frac{1}{VIF}$$

Autocorrelation Test.

Autocorrelation test aims to test whether the regression model does not deviate from the correlation between SMEs variables. The method used in this research is the Durbin-Watson test (DW test) with the following conditions:

- If (D-W) $< d_L$, then H_0 is rejected.

- If $(D-W) > dU$, H_0 is accepted.
- If $dL < (D-W) < dU$, then no conclusions can be drawn.

The test is carried out using the Durbin-Watson test, with the formula:

$$D - W = \frac{\sum(e_t - e_{t-1})}{\sum e_t^2}$$

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 3. Validity Test

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.637
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	77.697
	df	10
	Sig.	.000

Source: SPSS23

From the data above shows that the KMO and Bartlett's test value Asymp. The sig for each equation is above the specified alpha (0.05) which is 0.637. It can be concluded that the data is valid.

Table 4. Reliability Test

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.934	5

Source: SPSS 23

From the data above shows that the table of reliability statistics, Cronbach's Alpha value is ≥ 0.70 , which is equal to 0.934. It can be concluded that the data for variable X and variable Y are reliable.

Table 5. Normality Test

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test		
		Unstandardized Residual
N		10
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	.0000000
	Std. Deviation	1234964.789
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.154
	Positive	.094
	Negative	-.154
Test Statistic		.154
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.200 ^{c,d}

- a. Test distribution is Normal.
- b. Calculated from data.
- c. Lilliefors Significance Correction.
- d. This is a lower bound of the true significance.

Source: SPSS 23.

The table above shows that the normality test shows that, Asymp. sig (2-tailed) = 0.200 with alpha 5% ($\alpha = 0.05$). The conclusion is that the data is normally distributed.

Table 6. Heteroscedasticity Test

Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey			
F-statistic	2.443073	Prob. F(4,13)	0.0991
Obs*R-squared	7.724354	Prob. Chi-Square(4)	0.1022
Scaled explained SS	9.643114	Prob. Chi-Square(4)	0.0469

Source: SPSS 23

The table above shows that the heteroscedasticity test shows that the probability obs * R-squared = 0.1022 with an alpha of 10% ($\alpha = 0.1$). The conclusion is that these data do not contain heteroscedasticity.

Table 7. Multicollinearity Test

Coefficients ^a			
Model		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
1	Total of SMES (x1)	.152	9.351
	Total of Labor SMEs (x2)	.582	1.717
	Investment (x3)	.140	9.955
	Exports (x4)	.226	4.427

a. Dependent Variable: GDP(Y)

Source: SPSS 23

The table above shows that the variable data has a tolerance value of 0.152, 0.582, 0.140, 0.226 greater than 0.10 and has a VIF of 9,351, 1,717, 9,955, and 4,427 that is smaller than 10. The conclusion is that the data does not contain multicollinearity.

Table 8. Autocorrelation Test

Model Summary ^b					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	1.000 ^a	.999	.998	1656879.131	1.421

a. Predictors: (Constant), Total of SMES (x1), Total of Labor SMEs (x2), Expor (x4), Investment (x3)

b. Dependent Variable: GDP(Y)

Source: SPSS 23

The table above shows that in the durbin table know dL (0.2427) and dU (2.8217). In the Autocorrelation Test it shows that $d = 1.421$, so it shows that the data does not contain Autocorrelation.

Table 9. Multiple Linear Regression Test t Statistics

Model		Coefficients ^a		t	Sig.
		Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-77731158.8		-2.505	.054
	Total of SMEs (x1)	.1313	.635	.119	2.068
	Total of Labor SMEs (x2)	.120	.002	.955	55.669
	Investment (x3)	-3.844	4.632	-.054	-.830
	Exports (x4)	10.590	23.108	.013	.458

a. Dependent Variable: GDP(Y)

Source: SPSS 23

T test of number of UKM.

The table above shows:

- a) Ho: $\beta_1 \leq 0$ means that if the probability of t statistic > alpha then the variable number of SMEs has no effect on GDP. Ha: $\beta_1 > 0$ means the probability of t statistic < alpha, then the variable number of SMEs has a significant effect on GDP
- b) It is known that at alpha 5%, sig t statistic = 0.093. The conclusion is that the t test for the number of SMEs is that Ho is accepted with a probability > alpha (5%), meaning that the variable number of SMEs has no effect on the GDP variable.

T test of the number of SMEs labor

The table above shows

- a) Ho: $\beta_1 \leq 0$ means that if the probability of t statistic > alpha then the variable number of SMEs labor has no effect on GDP. Ha: $\beta_1 > 0$ means the probability of t statistic < alpha, then the variable number of SMEs labor has a significant effect on GDP
- b) It is known that at alpha 5%, sig t statistic = 0.000. The conclusion is that the t test for the variable number of SME workers is rejecting Ho with probability < alpha (5%), it means that the variable number of SMEs is significant and affects the GDP variable.

Export Multiple Linear Regression Test

The table above shows that:

- a) Ho: $\beta_1 \leq 0$ means that if the probability of t statistic > alpha then the export variable has no effect on GDP. Ha: $\beta_1 > 0$ means the probability of t statistic < alpha, then the export variable has a significant effect on GDP.
- b) It is known that at alpha 5%, sig t statistic = 0.666. The conclusion is that the t test for the export variable is that Ho is accepted with probability > alpha (5%), meaning that the export variable has no effect on the GDP variable.

Investment Multiple Linear Regression Test

The table above shows that:

- a) Ho: $\beta_1 \leq 0$ means that if the probability of t statistic > alpha then the investment variable has no effect on GDP. Ha: $\beta_1 > 0$ means that the probability of t statistic is < alpha, so the investment variable has a significant effect on GDP.
- b) It is known that at alpha 5%, sig t statistic = 0.444. The conclusion is that the t test for the investment variable is that Ho is accepted with probability > alpha (5%), meaning that the investment variable has no effect on the GDP variable.

Table 10. Statistical F Multiple Linear Regression Test

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1.599E+16	4	3.998E+15	1456.417	.000 ^b
	Residual	1.373E+13	5	2.745E+12		
	Total	1.601E+16	9			

a. Dependent Variable: GDP(Y)

b. Predictors: (Constant), Exports (x4), Total of Labor SMEs (x2), Total of SMEs (x1), Investment (x3)

Source: SPSS 23

The table above shows that:

- a) Ho: $\beta_1 \leq 0$ means that if the probability f statistic > alpha then variable X has no effect on variable Y. Ha: $\beta_1 > 0$ means probability f statistic < alpha then variable X has a significant effect on variable Y.
- b) It is known that at alpha 5%, the probability f statistic = 0.000. The conclusion is the investment variable f test is that Ho is rejected with a probability < alpha (5%), it means that the variable X is significant and affects the variable Y.

Effect of the Total of SMEs on GDP

Based on the results of the t test, the total of SMEs has no effect in Indonesia. The results of this test support the research conducted by (Hapsari et al. 2014) dan Nasution (Nasution 2018), in contrast to the research of (Resalawati 2011) which shows that there is a positive and significant relationship between the total of SMEs and GDP. SMEs are small and medium enterprises that are owned by individuals or business entities that are not subsidiaries. This shows that the total of SMEs is still too small to influence GDP. One of the causes of the variable total of SMEs is not significant to GDP, namely insufficient funding and also due to non-fulfillment of permits or requirements for capital

assistance, resulting in a decline in the development of SMEs. The increase in the total of SMEs will absorb a lot of workforce which will increase GDP. This test proves that the role of SMEs in increasing GDP is less contributing and proves that the development of SMEs is not optimal

The Effects of the Total Labor of SMEs on GDP.

Based on the results of the t test, the total labor of SMEs has a significant effect on GDP. The results of this test are in accordance with the research conducted by (Hapsari et al. 2014) which shows that there is a positive and significant relationship between the total labor of SMEs and GDP, but it is different from (Resalawati 2011) which shows that there is no influence between the total labor of SMEs and GDP. An increase in labor will increase everyone's income so that it will affect GDP. If the total labor has no effect on GDP, the average person has a small salary and high unemployment, and vice versa.

Effects of Exports on GDP

Based on the results of the t test, exports have no effect on GDP. The results of this test contradict (Resalawati 2011) and Nasution (Nasution 2018) with research which shows that there is a positive and significant relationship between exports and GDP. Exports are trading activities abroad by selling products. This research proves that the export activity is very small to affect GDP, so it is necessary to increase export activities so that it can contribute a lot to GDP. Increasing export activities will increase state income through taxes. Increasing export activities can also increase the number of businesses in a country, labor and investment, so that exports are very profitable for the country's GDP. If small exports indicate that the products of a business are still not in demand by the global market, there is a need for further development of SMEs.

Effect of Investment on GDP.

Based on the results of the t test, investment has no effect on GDP. The results of this test indicate that 0.444 is greater than 0.05. One of the reasons that investment does not affect GDP is that the use of public funding is greater for consumption than investment. This research is expected to increase public investment and reduce consumption of a product or service,

especially imported goods. This will help the government in developing the economy.

The effects of the Total of SMEs, Total of labor SMEs, Investment and Exports on GDP

Through the F test, the test results show that the variables of the total of SMEs, total of labor SMEs, investment and exports simultaneously have an effect on GDP with a result of 0.000 less than 0.05. The increase in the total of SMEs will encourage people to invest in exports and can create jobs that will reduce unemployment. This will increase economic growth. A qualified labor SMEs can increase economic growth. Labor is associated with salaries and wages, the better the performance of the workforce the greater the wages that are earned. High wages earned by energy. The increase in exports will encourage the development of SMEs, the wider the SMEs conduct foreign trade, the greater their business, so that it will increase company revenues, increase the total of employees, and can increase investment.

5. CONCLUSION, IMPLICATION, SUGGESTION, AND LIMITATIONS

Conclusion

Based on the statistical tests that have been done previously, it is known:

- 1) The variable number of SME units, the SME export variable and the investment variable have no significant relationship so that it can affect the GDP variable while the labor variable has a significant relationship so that it affects GDP. Simultaneously, the variables of the number of SMEs, the number of SME workers, exports and investment have an effect on GDP.
- 2) The factors that influence Indonesia's growth from 2009 to 2018 are the variable number of SME workers. The greater the number of apes' labor, the greater its contribution to affecting GDP. The number of SME workers cannot be separated from the role of the number of SMEs, investment and exports. The higher the number of SMEs, investment and exports will increase the workforce. Efforts are needed to increase these 4 variables. Quality Human Resources (HR) can foster the soul of entrepreneurs who can create new business businesses.

Human resource empowerment is the main key in the development of SMEs.

- 3) From the problems faced by SMEs, strategies are made to increase the productivity of SMEs. One strategy that can be implemented is the empowerment of the SME sector. Regarding funding, this problem has yet to be resolved, so it is necessary to make efforts by the government and society to help each other improve the Indonesian economy.

Implication, Suggestion and Limitations

- 1) In the era of globalization, the SME sector is required to be able to compete globally in order to increase its contribution to Indonesia's GDP.
- 2) The government needs to do more effective empowerment to increase the competitiveness of the SME sector. This is because the greater export opportunities in the SME sector increase Indonesia's economic growth.
- 3) Increasing the competency of labor or human resources also needs to be considered to improve the quality of products that have high value and high competitiveness as well.
- 4) Further researchers are advised to conduct research with the latest data with a long-time span and expand the variables, to determine the factors that significantly affect GDP.

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